

Gender Discrimination in Nigerian Politics 2023 General Election in Gusau, Zamfara State in Focus

Ibrahim Muh'd Bello PhD

School of Secondary Education,
Zamfara State College of Education,
Maru, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Abstract

Gender discrimination and political participation are widely contested issues among scholars worldwide, particularly those in Nigeria Zamfara State in particular. Gender mainstreaming has become a global practice in national policies across the globe. This study investigated gender discrimination in Nigerian politics 2023 General election in Gusau, Zamfara state in focus and explored practical ways through which political parties in Nigeria and in Zamfara state in particular can promote gender equality in the 2023 elections. The paper use Survey research design was adopted for this research. The study revealed that there was significant relationship between sociocultural factors. The study revealed that there was significant relationship between sociocultural factors (educational status and religion factor) and women's attitude towards participation in political process and that religion factor is the high predictor of women participation in political process in Zamfara State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that there should be strict implementation of the Acts and laws support women in the country, reserving certain percentage (35%) of political offices for women in the state. Also, any form of intimidation, harassment or act of violence against any woman venturing into politics must be severely punished, to encourage more women participation in the political process in Zamfara State.

Keywords: Gender Discrimination, Politics, Women, Electoral Process and Political Participation

Introduction

General Sani Abacha became the head of state in Nigeria after the coup in November, 1993 that ended the 4th Republic he dismissed the elected civilian governors and placed military administrators in charge of each state. In 1996 he created a number of state Ebonyi, Bayelsa, Nasarawa, Zamfara, Gombe and Ekiti. Abacha died in June, 1998 and he was succeeded by General Abdulsalam Abubakar who transfer or replace most of the Abacha appointees and 1999 General Abdulsalam Abubakar there was transition to civil rules in 1999 election was conducted and Olusegun Obasanjo became the president of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and in Zamfara State Ahmad Sani Yariman Bakura became the first civilian Governor of the state for two term. The second governor was Mamuda Aliyu Shinkafi and one term, the third governor was Abdulaziz Abubakar become two terms, the fourth Bello Muhammad Matawallen Maradun one term and the fifth governor and the present governor of Zamfara State Dr. Dauda Lawal.

The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria outline the fundamental right of the citizens in the country as follow: right to life, right to dignity of human person, right liberty, right to fair hearing, right to vote and be vote for, right to peaceful assembly and association, right to freedom of movement, right to freedom from discrimination.¹ Gender discrimination is when someone is treated unequally and unfairly based on their gender identity. Like all discrimination, gender discrimination is a human rights violation, though the distinction between "gender" and "sex" is a more recent development.² Take the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as an example, "Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of

any kind, such as race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.³

The outcome of the ⁴Beijing Conference of 1995 has led to giant strides in recognizing the need to accommodate gender issues in all aspects of livelihood globally.⁵ This is especially pertinent in view of the closing gaps in population distribution of the two genders. In the Nigerian context a National Gender Policy was developed and adopted since 2006, but not fully implemented widely. Current statistics appears that women are grossly under-represented in governance and excluded from the electoral process of 2023 General election in Zamfara State particular and the Nation in general.⁶

Although equal political opportunity for women is a goal shared by both men and women and despite increased support of women's equality, for thousands of years, women records poor participation in politics ⁷(Alkali, 2007). This is despite the fact that women constitute roughly half of the current world population ⁸(Bari, 2005). In Nigeria, like in other parts of the world, women are at least half the country's population. According to NPC report 2006 census, women constitute 48.78% of the national population, yet this numerical strength of women does not automatically translate to increase in women's participation in political process in the country.⁹ The participation of women in politics falls short of the desired 30% by international standards and 35% as entrenched in the ¹¹National Gender Policy 2006. Current statistics indicate that women are grossly under-represented in elective positions and excluded from the electoral process, such that in the 2007 elections, they constituted only 9% in the Senate of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 9.27% in the House of Representatives, 5.45% of the State Houses of Assembly and 0% of the Governorship and Presidential elective offices.¹⁰

Political participation is an essential component that is required for ensuring the stability and legitimacy of every political system.¹² Political participation is the sine-qua-non of democracy, because democracy involves a commitment to equal opportunity for men and women to develop their individual capacities.¹³ Thus, democracy appears to be inconceivable without political participation. Political participation therefore, describes the extent to which individual members of society share, take part or get involved in the life of that society. Consequently, the political power that women or any group of persons in a society have would be linked directly to the degree of their participation in the political process of that society.¹⁴

Political participation here entails various variables of participation but basically voting in elections and contesting elective public offices. This is quite different from representation. Representation basically entails elective/public offices held in relation to other representation. For instance, the increase of votes cast by women in elections from 10 to 40% of total votes cast in eight years signifies a form of increase in participation. But when the number of women holding public offices, when compared to men, is relatively low there is under-representation. That is, there may be an increase in participation of women and yet under-representation of women in politics; or there could be high representation of women in politics and yet low-level of participation, depending on the standards used to measure participation, however, the former is rather common.¹⁵

The right to democratic governance is an entitlement conferred upon all citizens by law. The 1999¹⁶ Nigerian constitution by virtue of Section 40 states the following:

Every person shall be entitled to assemble freely and associate with other persons, and in particular he may form or belong to any political party, trade union or any other association for the protection of his interests: Provided that the provisions of this section shall not derogate from the powers conferred by this Constitution on the ¹⁷Independent National Electoral Commission with respect to political parties to which that Commission does not accord recognition. Section 42(1) of the same constitution states further that:

A citizen of Nigeria of a particular community, ethnic group, place of origin, sex, religion or political opinion shall not, by reason only that such a person be subjected to any form of discrimination which is too open in Zamfara State. This further confirms that you can go to court to seek redress if as a woman your franchise is violated and that the constitution as a whole prohibits discrimination on the basis of sex. Section 77 of the Constitution also states:

- 1) Subject to the provisions of this ¹⁸Constitution, every Senatorial district or federal constituency established in accordance with the provisions of this part of this chapter shall return a member who shall be directly elected to the Senate or the House of Representatives in such manner as may be prescribed by an act of the National Assembly.
- 2) Every citizen of Nigeria, who has attained the age of eighteen years residing in Nigeria at the time of the registration of voters for purposes of election to a legislative house, shall be entitled to be registered as a voter for that election but women participation in politics was at zero level in Zamfara State.

Over the years, there has been raging debates over the participation or desire of women in Nigerian politics. With regard to political participation, women have been grossly underrepresented in Zamfara State in particular and Nation in General. The last general election revealed a 6 percent representation of women across all elected offices across the country. Some argue that women are regarded as weaker sexes which have neglected their meaningful and have placed them in a subordinate position to men in the nation's political system. The political enfranchisement of women in Nigeria politics seems to have maintained on the surface a level of gender equity politically, because it is assumed that constitutionally that there are no barriers to women's participation. Nigerian women General and Zamfara State in particular are contributing their quota to the development of the nation, but their potentials seem not to have been fully tapped due to low political participation. Disparities still exist between men and women in political participation in Zamfara State. This may be as a result of lingering constraints including poor economic condition of Nigerian women, patriarchy system, and unequal access to education, religious belief, and lack of assertiveness among women among others. Level of education, religious belief and men's perception on the need for women's participation in development have been viewed as determining factors in women's participation in political process, only three (3) women were given the position of commissioner and were given as a result of their parents influence in politics in the state because women lack political participation in the state one will wonder why women participation politics was lacking in 2023 ¹⁸General Election with no women that contested for presidency and Governor in the state. Against the backdrop of this study, this research work examined Gender discrimination in Nigerian politics 2023 General election in Gusau, Zamfara state in Focus.

Purpose of the Study

This study investigated socio-cultural factors as challenges of women participation in political process in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Moreover, the study examined the relationship between the socio-cultural factors (educational status and religion) and women's participation in political process. The study also examined the relative contribution of each of the socio-cultural factors to the participation of women in political process in Zamfara State.

Gender Discrimination

Gender discrimination in education is one of the root causes of [gender inequality](#) worldwide and Zamfara state in particular. Without a good education, individuals are severely limited when it comes to job opportunities. The consequences fan out from there, making a person more vulnerable to poverty, violence, human trafficking, poor health, and more. Globally, girls tend to be targets of discrimination. Gender inequality especially in the political arena is a serious challenge being faced by women in recent times. Gender inequality has been an issue for several centuries, the world over and Zamfara state in particular. Though history has it that fewer women have been in power even before colonialism. Instances are the Queen of Daura, the Sarauniya of Zazzau in pre-jihad, the Angwu Tsi who was almost the counterpart of the King, with her own Palace, in the middle belt, Iyayun the Queen who ruled in fifteenth century in Oyo, after the death of her husband.¹⁹ Though from the foregoing, it will be seen that very, very few women have had the opportunity in a leadership position, yet in every one or single case of women, there are several hundreds of the male counterparts.

Gender Equality, Political Participation and Sustainable Development

According to Dim and Asomah, gender often sets the expectations of both males and females and what each group can and cannot accomplish based on cultural and religious norms, which frequently inform legal, and legislative instruments deemed discriminatory towards female counterparts.²⁰ According to Kasomo, gender is not just about roles but also about relationships. Who established the regulations, and for what purposes are they related to what people claim women and men are or should do? In most nations today, men continue to dominate the political sphere Zamfara state is not exceptional.²¹ They frequently determine the rules of the game— laws, regulations, decrees, and policies in order to advance their interests over those of women. Women initially fought to get voting rights and the right to run for political office. Their male counterparts did not experience such restrictions in most countries, including Athens, where the notion and practice of democracy first arose.²² Gender equality, according to²³ Idike et al., emphasizes the examples of widespread and deeply established prejudice against women. In the past few decades, the majority of interest in gender relations has been driven by feminism, notwithstanding the general use of the term gender. Most feminists have portrayed gender relations as inequity and servitude.²⁴ However, gender is not merely the two-fold categorization of the social world as it is sometimes persuaded to be.²⁵ It is a cultural category supported by socially constructed (and contested) attitudes.

Major Challenges Upsetting Women Participation in Nigerian Politics

Women in Nigeria and Zamfara State in particular witness or suffer different discrimination such as: Uneven access to education, lack of employment equality, job segregation in the country, lack of legal protection, poor medical care, lack of religious freedom, lack of political representation Zamfara state is the theme of paper. The poor participation of women in politics and governance has been a major concern at the global level. In Nigeria, the number of women participating in politics is not proportionate to the 50% of the nation's population which they represent, and has not translated into equal representation in political leadership positions. Rising global focus on issues of gender equality, aided by calls such as that of goal three of the²⁷ MDGs Millennium Development Goals is bridging the gap created by long-term discriminations against women, and helping to make women more visible in politics. In this context, Nigeria has recognised women in the political sphere, and included them in both appointive and elective positions such as ministers, specials advisers in the federal ministries in the country.

Causes of Gender Discrimination in Nigerian Politics

The challenges facing women are enormous, however, researchers have shown that the under-listed are likely responsible for the huge marginalization of Nigerian women in politics.

1. **Patriarchy:** It refers to a society ruled and dominated by men over women, which in turn has given rise to women being looked upon as mere household wives and non-partisans in decision making process in households not to talk of coming out to vie for political positions
2. **Stigmatization:** Following the way politics in Nigeria is played, it is being perceived that it is for individuals that have no regards for human right and are quick at compromising their virtue for indecent gains. Therefore, women aspirants who ventured into politics are looked upon as shameless and promiscuous.
3. **Low level of education:** The low participation of women in education is also part of the shortcomings.²⁸ The National Adult Literacy Survey, 2010 published by National Bureau of Statistics revealed that the adult
4. **Financing:** Competing for political positions in Nigerian requires huge financial backup. Most Nigerian women who seek these positions could not afford meeting the financial obligations therein, despite the wavers giving to women aspirants by some of the political parties. And so, they could do little or nothing to outweigh their male counterparts.
5. **Political Violence:** Nigerian elections have always been characterized by one form of violence or another since the return of democracy. Female aspirants of various political parties cannot withstand political violence; therefore, women participation in politics is drastically reduced.

6. **Religious and Cultural Barriers:** Both Christianity and Islam do not accord women much role in public life, and same is obtainable in most cultural values, where women are seen culturally as quite submissive and image of virtue. However, they are not to be seen in public domain. And so it is a challenge to women participation in politics, more so, women found in the corridor of politics are not often religious in practice.
7. **Political Godfatherism:** This one of the concepts that open narrow doors when it comes to deciding who gets what in the political scene. However, it has effect on women participation.²⁹ Literarily, because Godfathers are seen in Nigeria to be men who have the power personally to determine both who gets nominated to contest elections and who wins an election. Godfathers are people of questionable wealth and influences who robbed political parties of their conventional and legitimate functions of presenting clear and coherent programmes on the basis of which the candidates presented by them are chosen by the voters.

Gender Discrimination in Nigerian Politics 2023 General Election in Gusau, Zamfara State

Descriptive research design was used to describe characteristic of a population or phenomenon being studied or situation without manipulating any variable. The population of this study consists of all women in the study area. A sample size of seventy five (75) female respondents selected from 15 government ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs) in Zamfara State and was selected through random sampling techniques. Questionnaire and interview items were designed for all the respondents under study, the items are intended to draw on information on Gender discrimination in Nigerian politics 2023 general election in Gusau, Zamfara state in focus. The questionnaire item is a multiple choice type, consisting of 29 items from which responses will be made. It carries two sections A and B for personal data of respondents and ‘Gender discrimination during the 2023 General election in Gusau, Zamfara state Nigeria. Simple frequency and percentage were used to analyse the data collected.

Table 1: Inadequate financial status of women affects women participation in political process:

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	50	66.7%
Disagreed	25	33.3%
Total	75	100%

Field survey, 2023.

In the table 1 above majority of the respondents agreed Inadequate financial status of women’s effect women participation in political process in Gusau having the highest percentage (66.7%] of the populace while 25 infrequency with 33.3% percent disagreed with statement.

Table 2: Religious belief is major problem hindering women participation in political process in Gusau

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	60	80%
Disagreed	15	20%
Total	75	100%

Field survey, 2023.

The table 2 above indicate that 60 respondents representing 80% agreed that religious belief is major problem hinder women’s participationin political process in Gusau. While 15 respondents representing 20% disagreed with statement.

Table 3: Patriarchal Cultural Belief is the Problems hinder women participation and representation of politics in Zamfara State

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	75	100%

Disagreed	0	0%
Total	75	100%

Field survey, 2023.

The table 3 above indicate that 75 respondents representing 100% agreed that patriarchal culture in the society has become hindering for women participation and presentation in Zamfara State.

Table 4: Political Godfatherism became hindrance to women participation and representation politics in Zamfara State

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	75	100%
Disagreed	0	0%
Total	75	100%

Field survey, 2023.

The table 4 above shows that political Godfatherism indicates 75 respondents representing 100% were male dominant in nature.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it could be concluded that, financial status, religion factor, patriarchal culture of the society and Godfatherism are among the cause gender discrimination related to women's participation and representation in political process, the three (3) Commissionership given to the women was as a result of the parents influence politics in Gusau, Zamfara State. Interview conducted with the first executive governor Ahmad Sani Yariman Bakura said that the problems is from Islamic point of view on membership of political parties. Qur'an where Allah emphasized that all Prophet lead by good example, managed their society and encourage what is good and discourage what was bad.³⁰ Islam attached important to leadership to the extent that no matter how small the number of Muslim is any given situation may be, be it on a journey or a gathering a leader must be appointed who must be of the best of them in terms of spirituals, disposition, character and leader capacity. A submits that Hadith Prophet (SAW) instructed that Muslims ensure leader among them whenever they are up to three in a given community.³¹

Recommendations

Based on the following findings, it is hereby recommended that:

1. There should be strict implementation of the Acts and Law in the country, reserving certain percentage (35%) of political offices for women in Zamfara state.
2. There should be a reformation of religious institutions of the states to avoid discrimination against women's involvement in public life.
3. Education of women is a tool to give women exposure and confidence to compete with men. Great importance should therefore be placed on women education in Zamfara State.
4. Any form of intimidation, harassment or act of violence against any woman venturing into politics must be severely punished, to encourage more women to participate in the political process in Zamfara State.
5. Women should be given financial assistance when buying form to contest election in Zamfara State.
6. Patriarchal culture placed a women in the society should be wave out and to give women to participate and represent in politics.

Endnotes

¹FGN Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999).

²Declaration of Human Rights

³Ibid.

⁴Beijing Conference of 1995 Socio Demographic Prefictors of participation among women in Nigeria.

⁵R. Anifowose. Women Political Participation in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects. In Akinboye (ed) *Paradox of Gender Equality in Nigerian Politics*. (Lagos: Concept Publications 2004), 52.

⁶National Gender Policy Women's Participation and the Political process in Nigeria: Problems and prospects. *African Journal of Political Science and International Relations*, 4(2), (2006), 43.

⁷R. Alkali Nigeria: *The Challenges Women Face in Politics*. Retrieved on December 18, 2017 (2018).

⁸F. Bari, *Women's trade unionism and Political Participation: Issues and Challenges*. United Nations Division for the Advancement of Women (DAW)EGM/WPD-EE/2005/EP.12 (2005)

⁹NPC National Population Commission. The National Adult Literacy Survey (2010) Published by National Bureau of Statistic. 2006.

¹⁰Nigeria CEDAW NGOs Coalition Shadow Report. The Nigeria CEDAW NGO Coalition Shadow Report Submitted to the 41st Session of the UN Committee on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination against Women held at the UN Plaza New York. (2008), 6.

¹¹National Gender Policy (2006), 64.

¹²R. Anifowose, "Women Political Participation in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects," in Akinboye (ed) *Paradox of Gender Equality in Nigerian Politics*. (Lagos: Concept Publications 2004), 73.

¹³Ibid.

¹⁴M. A. Y. Lewu, "Women in Nigerian Politics," in Hassan A. Saliu (ed) *Nigeria Under Democratic Rule (1999 – 2003)*. (Ibadan: University Press Plc., (2005), 8, 1

¹⁵L. Koleilat., Women Political Participation, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, National University of Singapore, available at, <http://sc6214.wetpaint.com>, accessed on 8 May 2017. (2013)

¹⁶Nigeria Constitution 1999

¹⁷INEC General Election result 2023 General Election 2023

¹⁸General Election result 2023 General Election 2023

¹⁹Modupe Gender Inequality and Women Participation in Nigeria PhD Thesis. (2001)

²⁰E. Dim and J. Asoma, Socio Demographic Prefictors Participation among Women in Nigeria, 2019

²¹Kasomo Factors Affecting Women Participation in Electoral Protection in African Masano University Kenya. (2012), 57.

²²Kasa, Women Initially fought to get Voting Right and the Right to Run for Political Office (2015).

²³A.N Idike. R.C Okeka and Okore C.O, "Gender Democracy and National Development in Nigeria," (2020)

²⁴J. Sarker, 'Development Theory and Gendered Approach to Development A review in the Third World Influenced' *Soge Journals*. (2006), 86.

²⁵A. Waylen Gender, Third World Politics Buckingham open University Press, (1996), 92.

²⁶R.W Conell, *Theosing Gender* Sage journal (1985), 42.

²⁷K. Millet K. *Sexual Politics*. Ph. D. dissertation at Columbia University Published (1970)

²⁸MDGs Millennium Development Goals, Bridging the Gap and Creative Long Term Discrimination against Women (2006).

²⁹The Holy Qur'an 21:73

³⁰Hadith of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW)